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Preliminary Analysis of the Imperfective Aspect Markers Di- and Pepha- in the Meranaw Language

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Abstract.

This study aims to examine the usage, morphophonemic structure, and semantic distinctions of the imperfective affixes *di-* and *pepha-* in the Meranaw language. The research employed descriptive and comparative methods to collect approximately 200 words from native speakers and from interviews with elder Meranaws in Marantao, Lanao del Sur. The words were categorized into five semantic verb classes: action, emotion, cognition, communication, and experience. The findings revealed that both *di-* and *pepha-* express the imperfective aspect; however, there are significant differences in their distribution, morphophonemic structure, and semantic usage. The affix *di-* exhibits a broader range of application, while *pepha-* is more selectively used and conveys a stronger emphasis on the action. Not all Meranaw words are suitable for both affixes, necessitating careful study to preserve linguistic accuracy. The study recommends further in-depth research using fieldwork and comparative methodologies to enhance both theoretical and practical understanding of these affixes and the broader aspectual system of verbs in the Meranaw language.

Keywords: Meranaw Language, Imperfective Aspect, Di-, Pepha-, Aspectual System, Verb